

The Impact of GSM on Bursting Strength of Knitted Fabric

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ABSTRACT

According to Bangladesh Export Promotion Bureau (EPB) statistics, in the last fiscal year (2022-2023) is that nearly \$63.05 billion knitwear products were exported from Bangladesh, which is 3.42 % more than last year. A huge number of varieties of knit fabrics were produced by Bangladeshi knit manufacturers, among them, most of the products are single jersey plain or single jersey derivatives structure such as single lacoste, double lacoste, polo pique, fleece, etc. Grams per Square meter, commonly known as GSM, is one of the most important parameters for the knit fabric manufacturing process. The strength of the knit fabric is also an important consideration from the buyer's perspective. In this present study, the authors found out how various knitted fabric GSM affects on the knit fabric bursting strength. We collected single jersey, lycra single jersey, interlock, waffle & 2X2 rib knitted fabric samples and measured their GSM values. After that, we analyzed fabric GSM on effect bursting strength of common knitted fabrics and found that higher GSM fabric shows higher bursting strength and vice versa. A study on the Impact of GSM Bursting Strength of Knitted Fabrics is done in this work. We have performed bursting strength tests on different GSM knitted fabrics.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the global knitwear market has witnessed significant growth, with Bangladesh being a major player in knit fabric production and export. Among the various knit fabric structures, single jersey derivatives (such as plain, polo pique, double lacoste, and fleece) are widely manufactured [1]. Understanding the relationship between fabric structure, GSM, and bursting strength is crucial for both manufacturers and buyers. The knit fabrics are more comfortable than woven fabrics, so the productivity of knit goods is increasing day by day. A wide range of diversified knit fabric production has also increased its new export market all around the world [2]. A wide range of knitwear can be found using various types of yarn, different types of fabric structures design and varying stitch lengths. Knit fabrics produced

from different parameters also show various dimensional properties. About 90% of knit fabric is produced by plain knitting. A large number of knit goods are produced in our country, such as T-shirts, underwear, stockings, socks, sweaters, etc. Moreover, knit fabric is widely preferred over woven fabric due to its lower manufacturing cost, comfortable properties, and easy manufacturing process [3]. For producing different types of knit fabric patterns, there are the use of different machinery arrangements with different loop stitches. Both the Physical and mechanical properties of knitted fabrics are influenced by the fabric structure as well as their knitting parameters. In most of cases of the dimensional properties of knit depend on yarn count, machine gauge, stitch length, etc. On the other hand, different loop arrangements, yarn twist direction, GSM, and tightness factor also influenced knit fabric's

dimensional properties. Some other special properties, such as rigidity, air permeability, bursting strength, and gram per square meter (GSM) of the fabric, are changed with a change in loop length. Bursting strength is an important parameter for the fabric manufacturing process [4]. Most of the buyers prefer knit fabrics having a good bursting strength for making ready-made garments. Various fabric structures have a positive effect on their corresponding bursting strengths. In some studies, authors found that strength and knit fabric extension are inversely correlated. Some other researchers showed that various fibers have a direct influence on the bursting strength of knit fabric. Gram per Square meter, commonly known as GSM is one of the most important parameters from the buyer's aspect. According to various studies, it is very difficult to predict the bursting strength of knitted fabrics before performing strength tests. In this study, we tried to collect various knitted fabrics such as single jersey, lycra single jersey, interlock, waffle & 2X2 rib, and then measured GSM and eventually examined how GSM affects on knit fabric bursting strength [5].

the base period. We refer to this as the Laspeyres approach. In the second, amounts consumed over the time period are used in each index's concerns which is the Paasche approach. The study uses a weighted arithmetic mean to calculate the average of the 20 samples.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Background:

Textile industries are one of the major revenue-generating industries in Bangladesh. Greater efforts are taken in manufacturing good-quality knitted fabrics. Bursting strength is a major characteristic of knitted fabric. It is responsible for the longevity of knitted fabric cloths [5].

2.2 Knitted Fabric:

Knit fabric is an elastic material made by looping yarns and interconnecting them to create a textile structure. They are comfortable, lightweight, wrinkle-resistant fabrics that make them ideal for travel. This fabric is used in athletic clothing due to its stretch and flexibility [6]. Knitted fabrics are more cost-effective due to their simplicity and quick production process. Knit fabric is used in a lot of athletic and leisurewear today. Most of your t-shirts and sweatshirts are made from knit fabric.

Such as t-shirts, leggings, tank tops, and sports bras are made from knit fabric.

Figure 1: Knitted fabric

2.3 Gram Per Square Meter (GSM):

GSM (grams per square meter) measures fabric weight and greatly influences fabric properties like thickness, stiffness, drape, breathability, and thermal performance. Controlling GSM during production helps avoid unnecessary costs and ensures quality, especially in knitted fabrics. Yarn count affects GSM, allowing engineers to compare fabric weights per unit area to determine which are heavier or lighter [7].

Figure 2: GSM Sample

2.4 GSM Determination Methods:

There are several methods to determine fabric GSM (Grams per Square Meter). The Cut and Weight Method involves cutting a small fabric sample, weighing it, and calculating GSM based on the weight and area. The GSM Cutter Method uses a specialized tool to cut the fabric, ensuring more consistent results [8]. The Weighing Scale Method involves weighing a larger piece of fabric and calculating GSM using the total area and weight. Automatic GSM Testing Machines streamline the process by automatically cutting, weighing, and calculating GSM, offering speed and accuracy,

albeit at a higher cost. Each method varies in precision, cost, and efficiency depending on the application [9].

2.5 Bursting Strength:

Bursting strength measures a fabric's ability to withstand pressure before rupturing. It's crucial for materials like upholstery, gloves, and technical textiles. Testing methods include the diaphragm and ball methods. Factors like fabric structure and yarn type influence its strength. High bursting strength ensures durability and performance, helping manufacturers assess fabric quality [10].

3. METHODOLOGY:

3.1 Principle of GSM Measuring:

The mass per unit area was determined by maintaining a standard testing atmosphere to reach the equilibrium atmospheric condition. The sample specimens were cut according to dimension and then weighed. After that, the sample mass per unit length was calculated.

Formula: The formula for calculating gram per square meter (GSM) gm/m^2

Gram per Square Meter (GSM) = (Weight of Sample in Grams x 1000)/ Area of sample in cm^2

3.2 Principle of Bursting Strength:

Bursting strength is a process to identify the strength of the material that is stressed in all directions. Normally, the readings were noted in KPa.

A test specimen is clamped over an expansive diaphragm by means of a circular clamping ring. Increasing air pressure is applied to the underside of the diaphragm, causing distension of the diaphragm and the fabric. The pressure is increased smoothly until the test specimen bursts. The bursting strength and bursting distension are determined.

3.3 Property of Method:

Method for determination of GSM: The GSM cutter method has been used in this experiment to determine the GSM of the sample fabric.

GSM cutter method: A GSM cutter is a specialized tool that cuts a precise area of fabric. The cut sample is then weighed, and the GSM is calculated based on the weight and the area of the sample.

Method for determination of bursting strength: The Diaphragm method has been used in this experiment to determine the bursting strength of the sample fabric.

Diaphragm method: The fabric is clamped over an expandable diaphragm, which is then inflated until the fabric bursts.

3.4.Determination of GSM by GSM Cutter

Method:

3.4.1 Steps of GSM Measuring:

First, cut a known-size fabric sample that reflects the characteristics of the fabric in order to measure GSM. Using a calibrated scale, precisely weigh the sample in grams. Next, determine the area in square meters by measuring the sample's length and width in centimeters, converting them to meters. Lastly, divide the sample's weight by its area to find the GSM.

Flowchart of work:

5 swatches are cut from different portions of fabric using GSM cutter

cutting area of GSM cutter = 100 cm^2

Weight of 5 swatches in gm are checked individually on electric balance

Average Weight of 5 swatches in gm are calculated.

Suppose the average weight of 5 swatches is 0.80 gm

Multiplying the average weight (0.80) with 100, we get GSM

3.4.2 Procedure of GSM Measuring:

To eliminate wrinkles, a large fabric swatch was prepared, avoiding selvedge and creases, and

conditioned for a day at $27 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $65 \pm 2\%$ RH. A GSM cutter was used to cut 100 cm^2 samples, and an electric balance was used to weigh them. Lastly, the fabric's GSM was determined by multiplying the sample weight by 100.

Figure 3: GSM Cutter using procedure

3.4.3 Steps for Bursting Strength Test:

Sample Preparation: Cut a circular sample of the material to be tested. Ensure the sample is free from defects.

Diaphragm Assembly: Place the sample over a circular diaphragm. Secure the sample to the diaphragm.

Pressure Application: Place the diaphragm assembly in a testing machine. Gradually increase the pressure until the sample bursts.

Data Recording: Record the maximum pressure reached before the sample fails.

3.4.4 Procedure of Bursting Strength Test:

In order to avoid folds, creases, selvages, and unrepresentative areas, samples were chosen based on fabric specifications. In accordance with ASTM D1776-08, samples were conditioned for 24 hours at $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $65 \pm 2\%$ relative humidity using the ISO 13938-2 method and a TESTEX tester. After carefully clamping each sample, a diaphragm was used to apply pressure until the fabric burst. The clamp was promptly released upon rupture, and the bursting strength was measured in kilopascals (kPa).

[4]

Figure 4: Bursting Strength Tester

3.5 Preparation of Materials :

3.5.1 Sample of Knitted Fabric:

Made on circular or flat knitting machines, single jersey fabric is a simple, single-knit fabric with uniform weft stitches and noticeable stretch that is created by knitting a single yarn row with needles or machines. The 2x2 rib knit creates parallel ribs with high stretch and recovery, perfect for fitted clothing, by alternating two knitted and two purled stitches. A thicker, double-knit fabric with two sets of needles, interlock creates a reversible, long-lasting fabric with smooth surfaces on both sides. Made on double jersey machines, waffle knitted fabric, also known as honeycomb, has a three-dimensional, textured, and absorbent pattern that promotes airflow and rapid drying. Stretch, recovery, and density are added by the cotton-spandex blend known as Lycra single jersey, which is typically composed of 95% cotton and 5% spandex and comes in 2-way or 4-way stretch.

Figure 5: Single Jersey-5 pieces, 2X2 Rib-2 pieces, Interlock-1 pieces, Waffle- 1 pieces & Lycra Single Jersey-1 pieces

4. DATA ANALYSIS & FINDINGS

4.1 GSM Measuring Result:

Table 4.1: Determination of GSM for knitted fabric

Sl No.	Fabric Type	Weight of 100 cm ²	Convert to Meter	GSM gm/m ²
1	Single Jersey	1.6	100	160
2	Single Jersey	1.85	100	185
3	Single Jersey	2	100	200
4	Single Jersey (Polyester)	2.2	100	220
5	Single Jersey	2.5	100	250
6	Lycra Single Jersey	2.5	100	250
7	Interlock	2.75	100	275
8	Waffle	2.9	100	290
9	2X2 Rib	3.2	100	320
10	2X2 Rib	3.5	100	350

From the GSM data chart analysis, it can be shown that 2x2 rib fabric shows maximum GSM then waffle, interlock, lycra Single jersey lastly the lowest GSM found in single jersey knitted fabric.

4.2 Bursting Strength Test Result:

Table 4.2 Determination of bursting strength for knitted fabric

Sl No.	Fabric Type	GSM (gm/m ²)	Bursting Strength (kg/cm ²)	Bursting Time (Second)	Bursting Pressure (kPa)
1	Single Jersey	160	528.7	18.0	649.8
2	Single Jersey	185	590.7	17.5	710.9
3	Single Jersey	200	676.8	16.6	798.5
4	Single Jersey (Polyester)	220	891.1	19.7	1000.7
5	Single Jersey	250	637.0	18.4	755.0
6	Lycra Single Jersey	250	350.6	21.9	500.4
7	Interlok	275	467.5	19.2	583.6
8	Waffle	290	359.4	16.0	475.3
9	2X2 Rib	320	793.2	17.5	906.6
10	2X2 Rib	350	888.7	17.0	1001.4

From the bursting strength data chart analysis, it can be clearly understood that the 2X2 Rib fabric showed maximum bursting strength as it had the maximum GSM, then sequentially lower GSM fabrics needed less bursting strength for the burst. A lycra single jersey knit has minimum GSM so it needs minimum bursting strength for the rapture. Single jersey (polyester) fabric showed maximum bursting strength for its yarn characteristics.

4.3 Impact of GSM on Bursting Strength:

Fabric weight, thickness, and density are measured in grams per square meter, or GSM; thicker, denser fabric has a higher GSM. Bursting strength, which is crucial for applications under stress, is the highest pressure a fabric can bear before breaking. After analyzing ten knitted fabrics, this study discovered that 2x2 rib fabric had the highest GSM and bursting strength, followed by waffle, interlock, Lycra single jersey, and finally single jersey, which had the lowest GSM and bursting strength. GSM and bursting strength were reduced in waffle, interlock, and Lycra single jersey fabrics

as stitch length increased. Because of their density, heavier (higher GSM) fabrics generally take more force to burst.

4.4 Aspect to Consider for Bursting Strength:

Denser, thicker fabrics with higher GSM have greater bursting strength, while lighter, lower GSM fabrics are less resistant to rupture. There is a direct positive correlation between GSM and bursting strength; however, factors like fabric structure, stitch length, yarn count, and finishing treatments also play important roles. Enhancing bursting strength requires increasing GSM along with optimizing fabric construction and finishing processes.

5. Conclusion:

This study looked at how GSM affected knitted fabrics' bursting strength. Although this inverse relationship with tightness defies theoretical expectations, it was discovered that bursting strength generally decreases as GSM and the tightness factor increase. While interlock and lycra single jersey fabrics are medium-heavy and require moderate bursting strength, single jersey fabrics are lighter than 2x2 rib and waffle fabrics because of structural differences. Greater bursting strength is required for fabrics with higher GSM. These relationships were evaluated using regression and correlation analysis, but more investigation is required to examine other variables influencing bursting strength.

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